

THE FIRST TEACHER OF BHAUDDIN NAQSHBAND

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ABSTRACT: The article is about the founder of tariqah Naqshbandiya, the first teacher of Muhammad ibn Muhammad al-Buxoriy, known as Bahauddin Naqshband(1318-1389), the fifth feast of the holy Bukhara, the great Muhammad Boboi Samosi (died in Samos village of Bukhara, in 736 hijri year/1335-1336 ms), a feast of the 14th ring of the Sufi tariqah of Khojagan, the perfect student of Khazrat Azizon (Khoja Ali Rometani), the teacher who discovered Amir Kulol, the great representative of Khojagon Sufism education, The article substantiates the role of Muhammad Boboi Samosi in the development of Bahauddin Naqshband.

Keywords: Khodjagon, tariqat, perfection, fifth feast, Muhammad Boboi Samosi, Bahauddin Naqshband, honesty, sobriety, foresight, positive forces, «The God is in heart, and hands are in work».

Muhammad Boboi Samosi (died in Samos village of Bukhara, in 736 hijri year/ 1335-1336 ms) is the first teacher of Bahauddin Naqshband (the founder of Naqshbandiya education), the perfect student of Khazrat Azizon (Khoja Ali Rometani), the teacher who discovered Amir Kulol, the great representative of Khojagon Sufism education, The fifth pir of world renowned Bukhara`s Seven Pirs¹.

He was born in Rometan district, Samos village. Boboi Samosi`s sacred tomb is in the same place. Khoja Boboi Samosi had four student after their teacher who

¹Navruzova G. Muhammad Boboi Samosi. /Place of Xoja Muhammad Boboi Samosi in the Nakshbandiya tariqah. Bukhara: "Buxoro", 2008. 15-28 pages, Navruzova G., Xoja Bahauddin Naqshband`s life and spiritual heritage. Toshkent: Academy of sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Fan" publishing state-owned enterprise, 2021. P 33-38. Navruzova G., Sayyid Amir Kulol-Bahauddin Naqshband`s teacher. Academia An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal Vol/11, Issue 10, October 2021. Impact Factor: SJIF 2021=7.492. 2109-2116 pages. Rahimov K. Hoja Muhammad Boboi Samosi`s life and work. / "Modernization of Islamic culture and stable development of tourism perspectives". International science-practical conference. 24 February 2020, Bukhara. 2020. 86-90 pages, Sadridin Salim Bukhari, Samad Azimov. Hazrat Boboi Samosi-great educator. /Place of Xoja Muhammad Boboi Samosi in the Nakshbandiya tariqah. Bukhara: "Buxoro", 2008. 3-14 pages,

were busy to educate faithful people.² His appearance was swarthy, light, emotional man, he had impressive look and solid opinion.

The job of Khoja Muhammad Samosi was farming. There is some information about Boboi Samosi in the source like Muhammad Boqir's "Maqomoti Shohi Naqshband", Mavlon Shahobiddin's "Maqomoti Sayid Mir Kulol", Nosiriddin Tura's "Tuhfat Az-zoirin", "Nazm us silsila" and etc.

Muhammad Boboi Samosi got great prophecy and could forecast. Bahauddin told a story about him: "It was The God's Great gift than Khoja Muhammad Boboi Samosi noticed me and adopted in my childhood. Before my birth Boboi Samosi passed through Qasri Hinduvon several times and told: "There is the smell of one hero here in the quickest time Qasri Hinduvon turns into Qasri Orifon." Once returning from Amir Kulol's residence to Qasri Orifon he said: The smel has been strengthen, it seems to me the hero has been born yet." Then visited to Qasri Orifon. It passed three days from the birth of Bahauddin. Bahauddin's grandfather was the adorer of Khoja Muhammad Boboi Samosi. He wanted to carry his grandchild to Boboi Samosiy to look at, and carried. Boboi Samosi told him: "He is our son we adopted him." Boboi Samosi said to Amir Kulol: "Have a compassion towards Bahauddin, I will not forgive you if have any mistake!"

After that time there was a light inside Bahauddin and happened wonderful events with him.³

Muhammad Boboi Samosi according to Bahauddin Naqshband's will came Qasri Orifon and visited his grandfather. Grandfather had told about his marriage sitting in front of him, said Bahauddin. Boboi Samosi said: "We must accomplish this righteous work." My grandfather wanted to become this event in front of him, but my father wanted to become luxurious as a rule this event. Khoja said: "It is no time to luxuriate, we should not be late." My father did not know that neighborhood and denied Khoja's will. Khoja went to speak with bride's parents. It soon changed my father's mind to luxuriate the event and accomplished Bahauddin's wedding at his 18th age.

It is said that, Abdulholik Gijduvani spiritually educated Bahauddin Naqshband, told about Boboi Samosi: "you will meet him during your life time and

²Qozokov B. Nosir ad-din Tura ibn Amir Muzaffar al Khanafi al Bukhari. The teacher and Students of Khoja Bahauddin. Bukhara, 1993.13 p.

³ Abul Muhsin Muhammad Baqir ibn Muhammad Ali. (2019) Authority Hoja Bahouddin Naqshband. / Persian translator, foreword, commentary and dictionary author Mahmud Hasani. Tashkent: NMIU "Uzbekistan". 29 p.

you will get a headwear from him, all the illness will be lost because of you.”⁴ It was Boboi Samosi`s forecast of being Balogardon (person who lost the ill) Bahauddin Naqshband and himself handled Azizon`s headwear.

Conclusion

There are some words which proving that Boboi Samosi`s forecast rightly:

- Muhammad Boboi Samosi`s forecast about birth Bahauddin Nakshband.
- Muhammad Boboi Samosi`s forecast that Qasri Hinduvon changed into Qasri Orifon.
- Muhammad Boboi Samosi`s forecast Bahauddin Naqshband`s being the great saint.
- Muhammad Boboi Samosi`s forecast Bahauddin Naqshband`s being Balogardon, gave him Azizon`s headwear.
- Muhammad Boboi Samosi directed Bahauddin to educate to Azizon, knowing his death becoming near.
- Muhammad Boboi Samosi had a good sense of seeing, smelling, tasting.

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⁴ Abul Muhsin Muhammad Baqir ibn Muhammad Ali. (2019) Authority Hoja Bahouddin Naqshband. / Persian translator, foreword, commentary and dictionary author Mahmud Hasani. Tashkent: NMIU "Uzbekistan". 28 p.

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